

MOTIVATION AS AN INSPIRATION OF LEARNING STRATEGIES

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Annotation: In this article is written about the way of learning language. Learning strategies are the smooth road of learning target language. Motivation is one of the most important strategies. Relations among motivation, learning strategy use and achievement were examined. We have observed that strategies are the easiest path of learning language whilst this road is very boring without motivation.

Key words: Approach, learning strategies, target language, salience of mastery, performance goals, effective strategies, ability, achievement, emphasize, expectancies.

Obviously, a human being always tries to find an easy approach to any direction. The way of learning language is not an exception. Learning strategies are the smooth road of learning target language.

We know that, in past our ancestors learnt the second language analytically by training their grammar and vocabulary. Thus, there were not able to use their awareness practically. However, today's youth have more wide opportunities to practice both analytic and practical knowledge. Exactly, learners strategy preferences can be used to help them develop their learning and improving their target language. Learners can select their particular preferences to understand how they should:

- . **take information;**
- . **use information for effective learning;**
- . **communicate more effectively.**

Overall, motivation is one of the most important strategies. We studied how specific motivational processes are related to the salience of mastery and performance goals in actual language learning. One hundred seventy – six learners attending English courses for academically advanced learners were randomly selected from one of their classes and responded to a questionnaire on their perceptions of the course goal orientation, use of effective learning strategies, task choices, attitudes, and causal attributions. Learners who perceived an emphasis on mastery goals in the classroom reported using more effective strategies, preferred challenging tasks, had a more positive attitude toward the class, and had a stronger belief that success follows from one effort. Learners who perceived performance goals as salient tended to focus on their ability, evaluating their ability negatively and attributing failure to lack that the of ability. The pattern and strength of the findings suggest that the classroom goal orientation may facilitate the maintenance of adaptive motivation patterns when mastery goals are salient and are adopted by learners.

Relations among motivation, learning strategy use, and achievement were examined. Questionnaires were to high school students in geometry classes early and late in the semester. Path analyses were used to determine the effects of motivation (ability perceptions, expectancies, and perceived value) and use of learning strategies (metacognitive, general cognitive, geometry specific, and effort) on achievement early and late in the semester. Early, both expectancies and value predicted the use of strategies, expectancies and use of geometry specific and effort strategies influenced grades. Later, value predicted strategy use; geometry self –concept and metacognitive strategy use influenced grades. No sex differences were found. Results concerning motivation are congruent with previous reports. Strategy use findings suggest that teachers emphasize the use of content specific strategies early in a new course and metacognitive strategies later. To conclude with, we have observed that strategies are the easiest path of learning language, whilst this road is very boring without motivation.

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